

The Effect of School-Related Stress on Individuals with Tic-Related Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder

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Table of Contents

Abstract.....	3
The Effect of School-Related Stress on Individuals with Tic-Related OCD.....	4
Background.....	5
The Problem.....	7
Research Question	7
Literature Review.....	7
Literature Genres	8
Figure 1	8
Tic-Related OCD	9
Stress (Primarily School-Related) and OCD	10
Stress (Primarily School-Related) and Tics.....	12
Literature Summary	14
Methodology.....	14
Analysis.....	16
Conclusion	19
Acknowledgements.....	22
References.....	23

Abstract

Many people across the world experience tic-related Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder (OCD). Stress is a universal experience that everyone experiences in their lifetime. School-related stress, however, is caused specifically by pressure from academic studies and/or social situations faced at school. While there are studies covering the relationship between school-related stress and tics or OCD individually, there have been fewer studies focusing on comorbid tics and OCD. This paper aims to analyze how and to what extent school-related stress influences symptoms of tic-related OCD. Additionally, numerous studies researched the effect of stress on tic-related OCD yet focus less or not at all on stress caused by school. By covering the transdisciplinary aspect of mind, brain, health, and education (MBHE), this paper's goal is to discuss how all these factors relate to each other on a larger, broader scale. It was concluded that school-related stress worsens symptoms of tic-related OCD by producing excess dopamine in the brain. The process of how and the extent that this occurs is discussed throughout this review more in depth. By continuing to learn about this underresearched area of literature, progress can be made toward improving the quality of life for individuals who experience tic-related OCD.

Keywords: tic-related OCD, tics, OCD, school-related stress, school, stress, MBHE, dopamine, social.

The Effect of School-Related Stress on Individuals with Tic-Related OCD

OCD is a chronic mental health condition which is characterized by both obsessions and compulsions that are consistently time consuming and cause anxiety or distress (Singh et al., 2023). According to the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, 5th edition (DSM-5), obsessions are recurrent and persistent thoughts, urges, or images that are intrusive and unwanted, while compulsions are repetitive behaviors or mental acts that an individual feels driven to perform in response to an obsession (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). An example of a compulsion based on an obsession includes the urge to repetitively wash one's hands due to the obsession that they are "contaminated" (Guazzini, 2022).

Tic-related OCD is a subtype of OCD which, based on a DSM-5 diagnostic subtype, is marked by the experience of tics—sudden, repetitive movements or sounds that are involuntary (Jones et al., 2023)—along with OCD (Pringsheim & Piacentini, 2018). Tics can range from movements (motor) to sounds (vocal), such as jerking one's arm or making a whistle sound (Jones et al., 2023). While OCD itself is not a direct cause of tics, OCD and tic disorders are highly comorbid (Jalenques et al., 2024). Tic-related OCD differs from tic disorders (TD) such as Tourette's Syndrome (TS) in that they are generally driven more by compulsions and the urge to tic, rather than being completely involuntary (Conelea et al., 2014). Throughout the world, it is estimated that 1-3% of people experience OCD while another 1% of people experience tics (Franklin et al., 2012). Additionally, 20-30% of individuals with OCD experience tics while 22-44% of individuals with any form of tic disorders have OCD (Franklin et al., 2012). Although this data had been collected over a

decade ago, there have been little repeated studies conducted to measure the same statistics, implying such evidence is the closest estimate available.

Individuals who experience tics are likely to experience more frequent tic attacks when dealing with high levels of stress (Leisman & Sheldon, 2022). Leisman and Sheldon (2022) report that when external stressors activate the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis, higher amounts of dopamine are released, which furthers the excitation of tic-producing neural pathways. External stressors refer to any factor that induces stress, including but not limited to environmental changes, social experiences, and workplace events.

When looking into external stressors, a factor of stress in children and young adults is school and school workload (Reddy et al., 2018). For many students, the last two years of high school especially, which involve preparations for higher education entrance exams, are a period of intense anxiety, stress, and worry for young students (Stromájer et al., 2023). Many students deal with high levels of pressure due to intense workload, intense competition to get into college, and numerous examinations (Reddy et al., 2018).

Background

Much research has been done on tics in relation to OCD, with studies focusing on symptomatology (e.g., Mukai et al., 2021), factors that impact its severity (e.g., Tan et al., 2024), and its relationship with other tic disorders (TD; e.g., Yu et al., 2022); however, less is known regarding how school-related stress influences this. Yu and colleagues (2022) discuss the comorbidity between OCD and tic disorder. They found that OCD and TD are closely related and considered to etiologically overlap. Mukai and colleagues (2021) detail the connection between tics and OCD, comparing individuals with just OCD to those with tic-related OCD. They found that patients with tic-related OCD start exhibiting symptoms at an

earlier age, are predominantly male, have higher frequency and greater severity of specific symptom dimensions (including symmetry/ordering and arranging dimensions), and have a higher prevalence of sensory phenomena (the physical or mental sensations that are associated with urges; Mukai et al., 2021).

Additionally, research has been conducted on how stress impacts the frequency of tics. Psychosocial stress factors such as family-related stress and personal relationship stress have been found to exacerbate tics in patients with any type of TD (Tan et al., 2024). Bortolato and colleagues (2021) point to environmental stress as a pivotal influence for tic severity. For example, abundant evidence has documented that tic severity is associated with the intensity of stressful life events including losing a job or moving schools (Bortolato et al., 2021). Furthermore, much research has been conducted on the effect that stress has on individuals with OCD, with Mahjani and colleagues (2021) reporting that stressful life events contribute to the development of OCD.

Researchers are aware of the extent to which school contributes to stress, with it being a significant cause (Reddy et al., 2018) along with the effects of stress on OCD symptoms and the frequency of tics. While research may seem prevalent with an abundance of sources (e.g., Fernández et al., 2025; Vallani et al., 2022) discussing the relationship between OCD and school, taking a closer look reveals that the majority of these sources focus on how OCD inhibits an individual's ability to achieve their full potential in school. With such an abundance of research centered around OCD, tic-related OCD, school, and stress, it is important to narrow in on areas that have yet to be researched. The effect school-related stress has on individuals with tic-related OCD epitomizes an area of research that receives less attention due to its specificity.

The Problem

While stress as a contributor to OCD severity has been researched by a variety of researchers (e.g., Ferreira et al., 2021; Li et al., 2021), there are fewer studies on how stress caused specifically by school affects tic-related OCD. Li and colleagues (2021) point out that stress is one of the main risk factors for the development of the disorder and note that OCD patients have an impaired stress response. Similarly, Iverson and Black (2022) found that nearly all patients report that stress worsens their tics.

In terms of causes of stress, academic stress may be the single most dominant stress factor that affects the mental well-being of college students (Barbayannis, 2022). India's National Crime Records Bureau, for example, registered 1.8% of students who died by suicide due to failing examinations (Reddy et al., 2018). Similarly, cohort studies with vital statistics in Sweden estimated that the odds of a serious suicide attempt (SA) in students decreased 60% for each point (range 1-5) increase in its grading system (Orozco et al., 2018). Although stress as a contributor to OCD and tics as well as school as a contributor to stress have been extensively studied, the two have been understudied altogether in relation to each other.

Research Question

To address the gap in the literature discussed, this paper will aim to answer the question: how and to what extent does school-related stress influence the severity of tics and OCD symptoms in an individual with tic-related OCD?

Literature Review

In order to respond to the research question analyzing how and the extent that school-related stress influences the severity of tics and OCD symptoms in an individual with tic-

related OCD, this literature review is divided into three topics: Tic-Related OCD, Stress (Primarily School-Related) and OCD, and Stress (Primarily School-Related) and Tics.

Literature Genres

The reviewed sources were primarily peer-reviewed articles from academic journals specializing in related topics. Sources used were predominantly published within the past seven years to ensure accurate and up-to-date research. A majority of the literature was gathered from Google Scholar, covering the transdisciplinary nature of the Mind, Brain, Health, and Education disciplines. For research on tics, articles focusing on tics in relation to either OCD or stress was used. Any research gathered on stress focused on psychosocial or academic stressors, to certify relevance to the education field.

Figure 1

As shown in figure 1, this literature review was divided up into three subtopics by grouping together variable combinations of the broader categories. Each of the three

categories relate to each other to a certain degree. Tics/OCD and stress caused by school have a cause-and-effect relationship whereas tics and OCD have a comorbid relationship.

Tic-Related OCD

Tic-related OCD is a subtype of OCD that has potentially received the strongest empirical support, which was shown by the DSM-5's inclusion of a new tic-related specifier as of 2013 (Brander et al., 2019).

Brander and colleagues (2019) published an article in the journal *Molecular Psychiatry*, which specializes in psychiatric topics and undergoes extensive peer review to ensure validity. They researched the familial load of tic-related OCD in comparison to non-tic-related OCD. After gathering data on individuals from six Swedish national registers, they created sub-cohorts consisting of all twins, full siblings, half siblings, and cousins to analyze the risk of tic-related OCD among individuals in relation to genetic relatedness. The hazard ratio (HR) was higher across most types of relatives of individuals with tic-related OCD compared to those with non-tic-related OCD, indicating that tic-related OCD has a higher heritability and familial risk than non-tic-related OCD (Brander et al., 2019). Benatti and colleagues (2020) found similar results and included in their research of the relationship between OCD and TD and SA that tic-related OCD showed higher rates of positive psychiatric family history.

Benatti and colleagues (2020) researched SA and suicidal ideation (SI) in search of a correlation among patients with OCD and comorbid TD, referred to as Obsessive-Compulsive Tic Disorder (OCTD). After recruiting 313 outpatients with OCD (n = 157) and OCTD (n = 156) from nine psychiatric departments in Italy, they divided the sample into four subgroups. The subgroups consisted of: OCD with SA (OCD-SA), OCD without SA (OCD-

noSA), OCTD with SA (OCTD-SA), and OCTD without SA (OCTD-noSA). While no differences between groups were found in terms of SI, SA rates were significantly higher in patients with OCTD compared to patients with OCD (Benatti et al., 2020).

Many potential treatment options for tic-related OCD have been proposed, such as cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT; Pringsheim & Piacentini, 2018) and selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs; Jalenques et al., 2024). After extracting relevant publications from five medical databases, Jalenques and colleagues (2024) found several studies concluding that youths with OCD and comorbid TS/chronic tic disorder (CTD) could benefit from SSRIs to treat their obsessive-compulsive symptoms. According to Pringsheim and Piacentini (2018), children with tic-related OCD should in addition be given high priority for CBT as initial treatment as there is evidence to support the efficacy of remote CBT for OCD.

Stress (Primarily School-Related) and OCD

When discussing the effects of stress on OCD (primarily caused by academic pressure), Adams and colleagues (2018) included that it may lead directly to the development of symptomatology, such as additional obsessions and compulsions. High school and middle school students who reported stressful life events were 21% more likely to go on to meet criteria for OCD 12 months later when compared to students who reported no such events (Adams et al., 2018). However, Adams and colleagues (2018) limit their discussion to stress in general and its effect on generic OCD symptoms, with no mention of tic-related OCD. Similarly, Ferreira and colleagues (2021) further emphasize the lack of research conducted on stress as a contributor to tic-related OCD by focusing on OCD symptoms in general, failing to discuss tics. They assert that increases in general stress and changes in routines throughout life are features associated with the development and severity of OCD (Ferreira et al., 2021).

Raposo-Lima and Morgado (2020) and Debnath and Sarkar (2024) reported similar findings through differing meta-analyses in which they synthesized findings from other research articles, concluding that stress exacerbated symptoms of OCD. In terms of identifying factors that induce stress, various studies categorize school as a major cause of stress (e.g., Barbayannis et al., 2022; Reddy et al., 2018). Stromájer and colleagues (2023) emphasize the importance of addressing the stress induced by the school environment, potentially by integrating anxiety prevention programs into the school curriculum and within the local school environment, particularly for school-going children.

Additionally, Loscalzo (2024) discusses a new potential clinical condition, studyholism (or obsession with study), in relation to OCD, with it potentially being defined as an OCD-related disorder. Based on numerous previous studies (e.g., Loscalzo & Giannini, 2017; Loscalzo & Giannini, 2018), Loscalzo (2024) reviews literature studying how studyholism should be classified. Loscalzo and Giannini (2019) recruited 1,958 college students between the ages 18 and 60 and created groups based on their major areas of study. They then measured students' studyholism through ten various scales and questionnaires including the Study-Related Perfectionism Scale (SPS), Penn State Worry Questionnaire, Overstudy Climate Scale (OSC), and more. Through Loscalzo and Giannini (2019)'s findings, Loscalzo (2024) established that problematic overstudying is better conceptualized as an OCD-related disorder since the compulsion component better aligned with that of OCD than addiction.

The brains of individuals with OCD have been revealed to have abnormalities in specific brain regions (Yang et al., 2023). Yang and colleagues (2023) conducted a whole-brain voxel-wise meta-analysis to investigate differences of functional activity and gray

matter volume between patients with OCD and those without. While they found no significant difference between participants with OCD and those without (taking into consideration age in resting-state functional imaging studies), they found significant differences in functional activity among various regions of the brain. Such differences in regions that patients with OCD showed were increased spontaneous functional activity in the bilateral inferior frontal gyrus and bilateral medial prefrontal cortex/anterior cingulate cortex, as well as decreased spontaneous functional activity in the bilateral paracentral lobule, bilateral cerebellum, left caudate nucleus, left inferior parietal gyri, and right precuneus cortex (Yang et al., 2023). These regions are linked with depression, suicidal tendencies, and emotional/motoric responses (Peng et al., 2024; Xu et al., 2019).

Furthermore, while testing polygenic risk for OCD, Heinzl and colleagues (2021) used a whole-brain analysis of functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) data on 128 participants, including patients with OCD, unaffected first-degree relatives of OCD patients, and healthy controls. Supporting what Yang and colleagues (2023) found regarding abnormalities in brain regions, they found decreased neural activity in the bilateral inferior parietal lobule and dorsolateral prefrontal cortex in both patients and relatives, which also indicates a level of heritability (Heinzl et al., 2021).

Stress (Primarily School-Related) and Tics

Numerous studies have been conducted to give insight into the relationship between children with tic disorders and school (e.g., Tan et al., 2024; Ueda & Black, 2021). For instance, a study led by Tan and colleagues (2024) focused on the effect of psychosocial stress (stress due to social and environmental factors) on the severity of TDs, concluding that psychosocial stress (including school-related stress) is a consistent influence on tic

exacerbation in pediatric patients. While they discuss school-related stress, they do not mention tics in relation to OCD. Conversely, Carneiro (2022) mentions the effect that psychosocial stress has on tics in relation to obsessive-compulsive symptoms yet fails to connect psychosocial stress factors to school.

Ueda and Black (2021) found in a direct observational study where the researchers went to multiple schools to rate children's tics that at least one motor tic was noted in 47% of first grade students and 15% of sixth grade students. Other observational studies which used questionnaires revealed that tics were found in 22% of preschool children, 7.8% of elementary school children, and 3.4% of adolescents, with a similar tendency observed in other countries outside of the U.S. such as Poland and Spain (Ueda & Black, 2021). They acknowledge that tic disorders do not affect intelligence and that most children with tics have normal or above normal intelligence (Ueda & Black, 2021). However, Ueda and Black (2021) establish that detecting and addressing students' difficulties at school (e.g., providing extra time to finish tasks, establishing a private space to release tics) is needed to support their educational needs and enable them to reach their academic potential.

Iverson and Black (2022) support previous claims by Tan and colleagues (2024) about TDs and further mention TS, discussing the factors that exacerbate symptoms. They included that according to a survey, conducted by Bornstein and colleagues (1990), one of the most common factors that patients with TS and their families associated with worsened tics included the return to school (Iverson & Black, 2022). Some patients report that tics become worse in scenarios where they are particularly self-conscious of their tics, which oftentimes include school (Iverson & Black, 2022). Tan and colleagues (2024) similarly obtained ratings and reports of tic severity for 373 children with TS and CTD between

January 2018 and December 2020. They operationally defined stress using the Yale Global Tic Severity Scale (YGTSS) and deduced that family-related stress, personal relationship stress, and school-related stress were independently associated with increasing YGTSS global severity, total tic score, and impairment rating over time (Tan et al., 2024). This indicates a positive correlation; as external stress factors increase, tic severity increases as well.

Tics can be associated with neurological disorders and are thought to be the result of dysfunctional basal ganglia pathways (Leisman & Sheldon, 2022). Specifically, many tic disorders are caused by excess dopamine in the striatum (Leisman & Sheldon, 2022). In terms of school-related stress, psychosocial stress-induced elevations in cortisol levels (indicative of stress) have been directly correlated with amphetamine-induced dopamine release (Bloomfield et al., 2019). This suggests that as psychosocial stress increases, the spike in cortisol triggers increased dopamine, which cycles back to more frequent tics.

Literature Summary

With tic-related OCD garnering more attention as a subtype of OCD, research continues to expand on areas including but not limited to genetics (e.g., Brander et al., 2019), mental health (e.g., Benatti et al., 2020), and treatment (e.g., Jalenques et al., 2024; Pringsheim & Piacentini, 2018). Additionally, as researchers make conclusions on the effects of stress, primarily school-related, on OCD, studies will continue to emerge on its scientific background and the areas of the brain that are impacted. The relationship between school-related stress and the severity of tics is an area that will also continue to be researched. The evidence already gathered on how individuals with tics are influenced by academic environments provides insight to further support studies targeting impacted areas in the brain.

Methodology

In order to understand the connection between tic-related OCD and school-related stress in regard to psychology, neuroscience, health, and education, rudimentary research was conducted by reading peer-reviewed articles found through Google Scholar. Keywords such as “OCD,” “tics,” “stress,” and “school” were most frequently used to examine how tic-related OCD and school-related stress are related. Once it was established that this area in the literature covered all transdisciplinary aspects of mind, brain, health, and education, a more extensive search was conducted to find articles that were both recent and accurate. To gather research on each of the three subtopics, such keywords were used in various combinations with each other. For research on the first subtopic, tic-related OCD, “tic-related OCD” was initially used; however, this key word did not yield as many relevant sources as using “tics” and “OCD” did. Occasionally, “Tourette’s Syndrome” was excluded to keep the focus on tics in relation to OCD, rather than other disorders. For the second subtopic, stress and OCD, the words “OCD,” “stress,” “school,” and occasionally even “dopamine” were used. For the third subtopic, stress and tics, “tics,” “stress,” and “school” were used, which generated an abundance of sources.

With the frequent use of the date range search parameter offered by Google Scholar, most sources used were published after 2018, with the exception of four sources falling between 2012 and 2017, and a 2022 source referencing a survey from 1990. The parameters also ensured the use of peer-reviewed sources. Any sources found through the World Wide Web rather than Google Scholar were reviewed to ensure that they were still peer-reviewed and credible by noting the reputations and publication processes of the journals; for example, Pringsheim and Piacentini (2018). Pringsheim and Piacentini published an article at the *Journal of Psychiatry* which specializes in researching psychiatry and neuroscience. All

articles are first reviewed by an editor and once approved, are then sent for a peer review process before getting published to ensure credibility.

The sources were then inspected for validity of their methods and conclusions by cross-referencing them with other peer-reviewed sources that conducted similar studies to verify any claims. The authors and researchers were also checked for their level of education and affiliation with any universities and/or research institutions. Additionally, only journals specialized in the corresponding area of research were considered (e.g., *Journal of Psychiatric Research*). When operationally defining variables (e.g., stress levels, tic severity), both quantitative and qualitative data were used, with references to the DSM-5 when defining OCD. Kevin J. Black (e.g., Iverson & Black, 2022; Ueda & Black, 2021) and Yura Loscalzo (Loscalzo, 2024; Loscalzo & Giannini, 2018; Loscalzo & Giannini, 2019) were referenced multiple times in varying articles due to their specialization in TDs and studyholism, respectively.

Analysis

Overall, the collective body of literature on tic-related OCD and its relationship to school-related stress exhibited more results on the school and stress aspect than on tics and OCD. This was expected, as the relationship between school and stress is a much broader topic which relates to a larger portion of the population. There was surprisingly less literature on the effect that school has on the severity of tic-related OCD, with much of the research focusing on how tic-related OCD may impact a person's ability to perform in school (e.g., Fernández et al., 2025; Vallani et al., 2022). This could have been because of society's emphasis on the importance of academic achievement over mental wellbeing. While not much of the literature focused on the relationship between school and the worsened severity

of tic-related OCD, there was much more research on psychosocial stressors' effect on tic-related OCD as a more general topic. Furthermore, literature focusing on psychosocial stressors specifically highlighted school as an included factor (e.g., Bloomfield et al., 2019), which was used to make connections of how school as a stressor influences the severity of tic-related OCD (e.g., Carneiro, 2022). Additionally, many sources oftentimes included school-related stress in relation to either tics or OCD (e.g., Adams et al., 2018; Tan et al., 2024; Ueda & Black, 2021). When this was the case, the symptomatology included was compared to studies focusing on tic-related OCD (e.g., Mukai et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2022) to form conclusions about tic-related OCD being worsened by academic stress.

A portion of the literature pointed to abnormalities causing decreased spontaneous functional activity in the brains of patients with OCD in areas linked with depression (e.g., right precuneus cortex; Xu et al., 2019), suicidal tendencies (e.g., left caudate nucleus; Yang et al., 2023), and emotional/motoric responses (e.g., bilateral paracentral lobule; Peng et al., 2024). The finding that OCD is linked with disruptions to brain function was expected, due to its classification as a neurological and/or cognitive disorder. The link between OCD and the brain also ties back to the finding that OCD has a major genetic component (Heinzel, 2021), since the abnormalities Yang and colleagues (2023) found in these brain structures are not caused by environmental components, but rather hereditary elements.

Finding that increased levels of stress worsen tics and OCD was an expected finding, since both tics and OCD are linked heavily to anxiety and tension (Bortolato et al., 2021; Mahjani et al., 2021). Additionally, since schoolwork and tests take up a considerable amount of time and energy for not only children and teens, but adults as well, it was assumed that

school is a contributor to stress. Academic stress is potentially the single most dominant stress factor that affects the mental well-being of college students (Barbayannis, 2022).

However, it was unexpected to find that TDs and OCD have such a high comorbidity, with 20-30% of individuals with OCD having tics and 22-44% of individuals with any form of TDs having OCD (Franklin et al., 2012). This correlation may be because the drive behind compulsions and tics often stem from a similar urge for everything to abide by one's mental set of rules (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). Tic-related OCD is also a subtype of OCD that has potentially received the strongest empirical support (Brander et al., 2019), which was surprising due to a prior assumption that tics were underresearched. It was also unexpected to find that there is a higher risk of heritability for those with tic-related OCD compared to those with non-tic-related OCD (Brander et al., 2019). Tics are also much more common than initially thought to be, with at least one motor tic found in 47% of 1st-grade students and 15% of 6th-grade students (Ueda & Black, 2021). Another idea that was unanticipated was the connection between SA and OCTD. SA rates were significantly higher in patients with OCTD compared to patients with only OCD (Benatti et al., 2020).

Though much research was found on several aspects of the topic in the literature, such as the effect of stress on tics disorders, the relationship between stress and OCD, how school influences stress levels, and the comorbidity between tics and OCD, less research was found on how all of these factors relate to each other. There is still a deficiency in how specifically academic stress contributes to the severity of tics and OCD symptoms in an individual with tic-related OCD. Additionally, one may argue that plugging in key words such as "tics," "OCD," "stress," and "school" into Google Scholar results in 8,990 results; however, taking a closer look reveals that these sources are either: published before the past decade and are not

up to date, focused on only parts of the topics, or are inconclusive to the area of research. This is likely due to a lack of urgency to continue research on a condition that is not considered life threatening. This may also be due to the COVID-19 pandemic which led to a sudden decline in the ability to conduct experiments involving in person evaluations, as well as a major shift in school dynamics due to the transition to online learning.

The research question of this paper is: how and to what extent does school-related stress influence the severity of tics and OCD symptoms in an individual with tic-related OCD? Based on the studies gathered so far, this question is aligned with a gap in the literature. While research focusing on the different aspects of this topic have been synthesized to come to a current understanding, to further address the deficiency in the literature, additional studies analyzing the direct relationship between tic-related OCD and school-related stress are needed.

Conclusion

This paper aimed to address the research question: how and to what extent does school-related stress influence the severity of tics and OCD symptoms in an individual with tic-related OCD? The analysis of the literature leads to the conclusion that school-related stress significantly worsens symptoms in an individual with tic-related OCD by causing excess levels of dopamine in the brain. This conclusion was based on numerous sources (e.g., Bloomfield et al., 2019; Iverson & Black, 2022; Tan et al., 2024) that analyzed different aspects of the deficiency in the literature (tics, OCD, school, stress, etc.). Tics and OCD have a high level of comorbidity (~30%; Franklin et al., 2012), indicating the two are likely caused by similar/related factors. It was also noted that compulsions and tics oftentimes present themselves in similar ways—typically as repetitive movements or sounds (American

Psychiatric Association, 2013; Jones et al., 2023). After finding that OCD and tics are both worsened by increased levels of stress (Leisman & Sheldon, 2022; Mahjani et al., 2021), research then shifted to causes of stress. In sources analyzing the relationship between stress and tics/OCD, psychosocial stressors were listed as a significant factor (Tan et al., 2024; Bloomfield et al., 2019). Psychosocial stress factors, according to Tan and colleagues (2024), include school-related stress. It was further supported by Reddy and colleagues (2018) and Stromájer and colleagues (2023) that school is a major cause of stress. This was then used to connect school to a major exacerbator of tic-related OCD.

One limitation of the research process was the time given. There was little time to complete each step of the research process. If more time had been allotted, research could have been better analyzed and selected to provide more evidence for the conclusion. For future research, I recommend creating a preliminary outline with basic ideas of the structure to avoid unnecessary waste of time. Additionally, more time should have been spent on the analysis, and less on the literature review. While the literature review is a crucial part of the paper, the time spent could have been better put toward planning out how to write an analysis. Another limitation was the little research on tics or OCD that included school-related stress, as a majority of articles had been published over a decade ago and considered outdated. To combat this in the future, I recommend focusing on a few articles with high quality data, rather than attempting to synthesize an excessive amount of sources.

My initial research question focused on the relationship between the amount of schoolwork a student receives, and the frequency they experience tics related to OCD. However, this would have been difficult to measure, as every student may perceive the same amount of work differently. Additionally, there were fewer reports accurately describing the

amount of work students put in. Data varied across different ages, course rigor, socioeconomic status, etc. The findings will lead to more awareness for the amount of stress schools can put students under and how this may affect their health. Schools can start to consider ways to avoid worsened tic-related OCD by implementing mindfulness activities, rules against the amount of work allowed to be given, or even just reminders to students about how they deal with academic pressure. For future studies, I suggest focusing more on what structures of the brain are being affected by increased stress, and how this correlates with worsened tic-related OCD. The main part of my research focused on comparing the similarities between how school-related stress influences tics versus OCD. By focusing more on the brain, I could have strengthened the connection by noting certain parts of the brain responsible for stress response.

While it was concluded that symptoms of tic-related OCD were significantly worsened by school-related stress, it is still unspecified how strong this correlation is in comparison to other factors. Additionally, recommendations for future work include focusing on how stress levels are shaped by the varying levels of academic pressure that students place on themselves. Students who enroll in more challenging classes and receive a more rigorous workload would be likely to hold higher expectations for themselves and experience more excessive levels of stress. In the future, it is necessary for further research to be conducted on ways to counteract the worsened symptoms caused by school-related stress to ensure a better quality of life for individuals with tic-related OCD.

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